

INNOVATIVE UPGRADING OF TCR® INTERMEDIATES: PATHWAYS TO SUSTAINABLE BIOFUELS

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ABSTRACT: Within the European-funded research project “Phy2Climate,” an innovative biorefinery was implemented with the overall goal of combining phytoremediation and biofuel production for the maritime and transport sector. In the frame of the biorefinery concept, contaminated biomass harvested from the project’s pilot sites are initially converted into gaseous, liquid, and solid intermediate products using the thermo-catalytic reforming process (TCR®). These intermediates are subsequently upgraded by applying different techniques. The aim of this study is to investigate the feasibility of the production of Marine Fuels according to ISO 8217 only via an economical distillation process. First results indicate that already most of the parameters stated in the ISO 8217 are within the given thresholds of the norm. However, parameters like the water content, the density and the flash point still must be tuned to meet all specifications. For this, a mild hydrotreatment of the TCR® distillate is proposed. Furthermore, the Synol process is introduced as a promising alternative to highly sensitive Gas to Liquid processes like the Fischer-Tropsch process to produce liquid energy carriers from the gaseous TCR®-intermediate. The process offers various advantages as it is low-energy intense, as it operates under lower pressure and temperature compared to the Fischer-Tropsch synthesis.

Keywords: biorefinery, thermochemical conversion, thermo-catalytic reforming, distillation, marine fuel, ISO 8217, gas to liquid, synol process.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Biorefinery

The European-funded research initiative “Phy2Climate” (Grant Agreement No. 101006912) aims to create an innovative biorefinery that integrates phytoremediation with biofuel production [1,2]. This pilot facility, depicted in Figure 1, employs advanced biomass processing techniques to generate clean, drop-in biofuels suitable for both road and maritime transportation. Currently, the system is at Technology Readiness Level 5 (TRL-5), indicating that its core processes have been tested in relevant environments. Within this biorefinery, contaminated biomass collected from the project’s pilot sites undergoes a multi-stage conversion process. Initially, the biomass is transformed via thermo-catalytic reforming (TCR®) into high-quality gaseous, liquid, and solid intermediate products [3]. These intermediates are then refined to meet established biofuel quality standards. The gaseous byproduct produced during TCR® is utilized as feedstock in a Gas-to-Liquid (GTL) process, which aims to produce oxygenated hydrocarbons compatible with existing oil refineries as drop-in biofuels. Additionally, the oil phase is evaluated for its potential as marine fuel after distillation, while the aqueous phase is purified to extract hydrogen for the GTL process through electrooxidation [4].

Furthermore, the biochar generated during processing can serve as a substitute for petcoke in copper smelting operations. This application not only provides valuable use for the heavy-metal enriched biochar but also enables the recovery of the accumulated heavy metals within the smelting process, thereby completing the phytoremediation cycle. The focus of this publication lies in the individual upgrading strategies for the oil and the gas phase and the comparison of the final fuel products to standard fuels.

Figure 1: Biorefinery concept

1.2 Pyrolysis oil upgrade to Marine Fuels according to ISO 8217

Marine Fuels are classified into different grades based on their properties and intended use within ISO 8217. The standard specifies the requirements for various types of residual and distillate fuels used in ships' engines. It covers aspects such as viscosity, density, sulfur content, flash point, and other important parameters to ensure safe and efficient operation. The main fuel blends include MGO (Marine Gas Oil), MDO (Marine Diesel Oil) and IFO (Intermediate Fuel Oil) among others. ISO 8217 helps ensure that marine fuels meet consistent quality standards worldwide, promoting safety, environmental protection, and engine performance. The mentioned fuel blends (IFO, MGO and MDO) are blends of different distillation fractions (MGO) or blends of distillation and residual fractions of fossil fuels (MDO and IFO). MGO and MDO are classified as Distillate Marine Fuels whereas IFO blends are classified as Residual Marine Fuels. MGO and MDO blends include fuel grades like DMX, DMA, DMZ and DMB). IFO blends include fuel grades like RMA, RMB, RMD, RME, RMG (180/380/500/700) and RMK (380/500/700) [5].

To upgrade bio crude derived from classical pyrolysis e.g. from fast pyrolysis or single-step pyrolysis processes into marine fuels that meet the ISO 8217 standards, several key upgrading steps are typically necessary. These include

hydro processing to remove hetero atoms like N, S, O and saturate hydrocarbons; distillation is carried out to obtain the correct fuel fractions, followed by blending, and rigorous quality control to ensure compliance with ISO 8217 standards for marine fuels. These steps ensure that the final fuel has the required properties, such as low sulfur content, suitable viscosity, stability, and cleanliness [6,7]. Due to the exclusive TCR[®] bio-oil properties like improved stability, lower oxygen content, better compatibility with refining processes, and generally higher quality compared to typical pyrolysis oils. The aim within the project Phy2Climate was to verify whether the usually needed extensive upgrading process can be reduced to a simple and cheap distillation step offering a way for cheap sustainable Marine Fuels [8].

1.3 Gas to Liquid conversion routes for TCR gas

Gas-to-liquid processes for pyrolysis gases involve converting TCR[®] gas produced during pyrolysis to liquid fuels. These gases can be processed through GTL technologies to produce high-quality liquid fuels, such as diesel or kerosene, suitable for transportation and industrial use. The GTL process typically includes steps like gas cleaning, shift reactions to adapt the hydrogen concentration and catalytic synthesis, where the gases are converted into liquid hydrocarbons via chemical reactions like Fischer-Tropsch synthesis. This method offers a way to efficiently utilize pyrolysis gases, reduce waste, and produce cleaner fuels. However, especially efficient conversion technologies like the Fischer-Tropsch (FT) process have some important limitations related to the gas purity of pyrolysis gases. Since FT catalysts are sensitive to impurities, the presence of contaminants can significantly affect the efficiency and lifespan of the catalysts. Specifically, impurities such as sulfur compounds, nitrogen compounds, oxygenates, and particulates poison the catalysts, leading to deactivation or reduced activity [9,10].

Pyrolysis gases often contain these impurities, which means they require thorough and therefore expensive cleaning and conditioning before entering the FT reactor. This additional gas cleaning step increases complexity and costs [11]. Moreover, the gas must have a relatively high purity level, particularly low levels of sulfur and oxygenates in ppb range—to ensure optimal operation and catalyst longevity. To overcome the mentioned limitations and reduce the need for extensive pyrolysis gas purification, GTL processes like the Synol process which use cheap and easy-to-replace catalysts could be an alternative to the Fischer-Tropsch process [12].

The Synol process is a technical method for synthesizing aliphatic, straight-chain alcohols from a gas mixture containing carbon monoxide (CO) and hydrogen (H₂). It was developed in the 1940s as a response to the limited efficiency and product quality of earlier processes such as the Fischer-Tropsch synthesis. While Fischer-Tropsch mainly produced hydrocarbons – often with high gas consumption and limited economic value – the Synol process aimed to convert a greater proportion of the input gas into valuable chemical products, particularly alcohols.

The chemical basis of the Synol synthesis involves a reaction in which carbon monoxide and hydrogen, in approximately a 1:1 molar ratio, are passed over a highly reduced iron-base melt catalyst under moderate pressure (approximately 18-25 atm) and temperatures between 170 - 190 °C. This results primarily in normal alcohols ranging from C1 to approximately C16 (e.g., ethanol, propanol,

butanol, up to higher alcohols). By-products include water, CO₂, hydrocarbons, esters, and trace amounts of aldehydes. A key feature of the process is that it yields exclusively linear (non-branched) alcohols, distinguishing it from processes like the oxo synthesis, which can produce branched isomers. From a technical standpoint, the reaction can be carried out in multiple stages or, more efficiently, in a recycling loop configuration. In this setup, the gas mixture exiting the reactor is cooled, the condensable products are separated, and the remaining gas is reheated and recirculated through the catalyst bed. This enhances gas utilization, improves process efficiency, and extends catalyst lifetime by maintaining stable thermal and chemical operating conditions. Another advantage of the Synol process is the use of iron catalysts instead of cobalt, which was a scarce and expensive material at the time. Iron was cheaper and more readily available in Germany, making the process especially attractive under the resource constraints of World War II. In summary, the Synol process offers the potential to provide a more economical and efficient route for producing aliphatic alcohols from pyrolysis gases opening the doors for an implementation especially in decentralized biorefineries [13].

2 METHODS AND EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Oil selection and upgrading

Thermochemical conversion trials have been done for various biogenic feedstocks harvested during the Phy2Climate project. Based on the oil output during the conversion trials and the oil quality, three bio-oils were selected for distillation and compared to the parameters found in ISO 8217 for Residual and Distillate Fuels.

Oil distillation was performed under atmospheric pressure for a maximum boiling point of 370°C using a simple laboratory setup. The distillate was captured until no further distillate formation could be observed within the condenser at the maximum temperature.

2.2 Theoretical considerations to the Synol process

The stoichiometric equation for the Synol Process resulting from the reaction of the synthesis gas with the employed iron catalyst is shown in Equation 1.

As a result of the synthesis reaction, 2-hexanol and hexane are formed as primary products. Water and carbon dioxide are generated as by-products. The reaction is exothermic. Experimental results have shown that a CO:H₂ ratio of 1,05:1 constitutes the ideal composition. [12]

2.3 Catalyst preparation

The catalyst used in the Synol process is an iron-based fused catalyst. Its composition is provided in Table 1 and is based on literature research results [14].

Table I: Catalyst components for Synol process

Nr.	Substance	Fraction of substance in vol-%
1	Fe ₃ O ₄	97
2	Al ₂ O ₃	2,5
3	K ₂ O	0,2-0,6
4	S	0,16
5	C	0,03

The fabrication of the catalyst requires the mixing of an acidic solution (250 mL, 1 mol of $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ and 0.05 mol of $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$) and a basic solution (1200 mL, 1.2 mol of K_2CO_3) in a glass reactor at a maintained temperature of 60°C . The solution is constantly stirred at 200 rpm. The solutions are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Acid solution (left) and basic solution (right)

Both solutions are transferred through pumps. The flow rate of the pumps is manually controlled based on a pH value of 7. During the process, solids precipitating and a suspension is formed as shown in Figure 2 (left).

Figure 3: Suspension forming and precipitation during solution mixing (left); Catalyst after oven drying (middle) and after air drying (right)

After the precipitation, the formed granulate needs to be washed and filtered. This step was repeated four times. After that, the granulate was air dried for 24 hours and dried subsequently dried in an oven at 80°C under atmospheric conditions. The catalyst is shown after both dryings in Figure 3 (middle and right). To further improve the catalyst, calcination to remove remaining organic compounds and water as well as a reduction of the catalyst would be beneficial. However, these steps have not been taken within this study.

2.4 Synol trials

The conversion is done using a laboratory-scale plant which is divided into two main sections. A synthesis section and an analysis section. The system includes gas inlets for nitrogen (N_2), carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO_2), hydrogen (H_2), calibration gas and TCR[®] (Thermo-Catalytic Reforming) gas. The flow rate of each gas component is controlled by mass flow controllers (MFC). The gas components are mixed in a gas mixing unit, and the volume of the final synthesis gas is controlled via a control panel. The double tube reactor is temperature controlled via a thermal oil loop. The reactor pressure is controlled via a membrane system and a nitrogen-based pressure control. Pressure-controlled connections between the conversion reactor and the analytical part of the plant

ensure the transfer of samples for analysis. The analysis is done using a gas chromatograph with four detectors. Two flame ionization detectors (FID) and two thermal conductivity detectors (TCD). The first FID detects carbon chains $\text{C}_1 - \text{C}_7$, the second FID detects C_{7+} . The first TCD detects hydrogen (H_2), oxygen (O_2), nitrogen (N_2), carbon monoxide (CO) and carbon dioxide (CO_2). The temporal sequence of the measurements is controlled using a software called Multi Tec. Samples can be taken via the pressure-controlled connections before and after the reactor, allowing the quantification and calculation of conversion rates of the synthesis gas. Measurements are taken once per hour for each measuring pipe.

Until now, one initial conversion trial at a temperature of 190°C and a pressure level of 25 bar has been done using synthetic gases supplied from standard gas bottles. No recycling of the off gases has been implemented.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Oil selection and distillation results

Three oils from the former mentioned conversion trials were distilled. This includes the oil from the Herbaceous Mix from Lithuania (a mixture of tall fescue, perennial ryegrass, alfalfa, festuca perennis and bird's-foot trefoil), the oil from the aerial parts of Jerusalem Artichoke (also from Lithuania) and the oil from Sorghum (straw and the seeds) from the pilot site from Spain.

II shows the distillation efficiency for a maximum boiling point of 370°C under atmospheric pressure.

Table II: Distillation efficiency of the selected TCR[®] oils

Feedstock	Distillate in wt%	Residual in wt%
Herbaceous Mix	79.5	21.5
Jerusalem Artichoke	71.8	28.2
Sorghum	72.2	27.8

Until now, one of the produced distillates (Herbaceous Mix from Lithuania) was analyzed according to the specifications of ISO 8217 via an external analysis laboratory (Eurofins Umwelt Ost GmbH Freiberg, Germany). The results are shown in Table 3. The values in the table are color coded. In the column "Herbaceous Mix" corresponds green to the DMX, blue to the DMA, orange to the DMZ and purple to the DMB fuel grade. Red exceeds all limit values for the fuel grades mentioned. The color-filled cells indicate the minimum (green) and the maximum (red) limit values for the tested parameter according to the respective fuel grade.

As can be seen in Table 3 via a simple distillation of the TCR[®] oil from the biogenic feedstock "Herbaceous Mix" four out of the nine fuel parameters specified for Distillate Marine Fuels in the ISO 8217 can be fulfilled. The density, the water content, the Micro Carbon Residue, the flash point and the acid number succeed the specified limits. A reduction of the water content can be reached through the addition of a drying agent or a subsequent solvent extraction.

Table III: Eurofins analysis of the distilled oil from the biomass Herbaceous Mix (Lithuania) according to ISO 8217 :2017 Distillate (fuel grades DMX, DMA/DFA, DMZ/DFZ, DMB/DFB)

Fuel parameter	Herbaceous mix	DMX	DMA/DFA	DMZ/DFZ	DMB/DFB
Density @ 15°C (kg/m ³)	982.8	-	890	890	900
Viscosity @50°C (Eurofins) @40°C (ISO 8217) (mm ² /s)	4.3	1.4	2	3	2
Water (%V/V)	1.86	-	-	-	0.3
Micro Carbon Residue (Koksrückstand) (%m/m)	0.33	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Sulfur (%m/m)	0.25	1	1	1	1.5
Ash @775°C (%m/m)	0.007	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Pour Point (°C) (winter/summer)	3	-	-6	-6	0
Flash Point (°C)	35	43	60	60	60
Acid Number (mg KOH/g)	0.95	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5

Table IV: Eurofins analysis of distilled oil with biomass Herbaceous Mix (Lithuania) according to ISO 8217 :2017 Residual (fuel grades RMA, RMB, RMD, RME, RMG (180/380/500/700), RMK (380/500/700)

Fuel parameter	Herbaceous mix	RMA (10)	RMB (30)	RMD (80)	RME (180)	RMG (180 / 380 / 500 / 700)	RMK (380 / 500 / 700)
Density @15°C (kg/m ³)	982.8	920	960	975	991	991	1010
Viscosity @50°C (mm ² /s)	4.3	10	30	80	180	180 / 380 / 500 / 700	380 / 500 / 700
Water (%V/V)	1.86	0.3	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Micro Carbon Residue (Koksrückstand) (%m/m)	0.33	2.5	10	14	15	18	20
Ash @775°C (%m/m)	0.007	0.04	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.1	0.15
Vanadium (mg/kg)	<1	50	150	150	150	350	450
Sodium (mg/kg)	<1	50	100	100	50	100	100
Aluminium + Silicon (mg/kg)	5 +7	25	40	40	50	60	60
Calcium (mg/kg)	6	calcium < 30 and zinc < 15 OR calcium < 30 and Phosphorus < 15					
Zinc (mg/kg)	3						
Phosphorus (mg/kg)	<1						
Pour Point (°C) (winter/summer)	3	0	0	30	30	30	30
Flash Point (°C)	35	60	60	60	60	60	60
CCAI (Ignition Quality) (-)	923	850	860	860	860	870	870
Acid Number (mg KOH/g)	0.95	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5

The density is a function of the chemical composition of the distillate. Long-chained molecules lead to a higher density. Breaking down these components via e.g. hydrotreatment could lead to a reduction of density. An alternative would be the addition of low-density additives like methanol. If hydrotreatment is applied to the distillate, this could also have a positive effect on the Micro Carbon Residue and lead to a further improvement of the distillate. The acid number (TAN) of the TCR[®] distillate is compared to classical pyrolysis oils already very low, but still over the threshold for Distillate Marine Fuels. A subsequent mild hydrotreatment of the distillate or alternatively a solvent extraction of the acidic components within the distillate could lead to a sufficient reduction of the TAN to be within the limits of the norm. The low flash point of the TCR[®] distillate is likely due to the presence of low-boiling, high-volatile components. Therefore, a reduction of those components (which could for example be reached by discarding the first low-boiling fraction of the distillation product) should lead to an increase of the flash point to fulfill the ISO 8217 norm.

Table IV shows the analog comparison of the TCR[®] distillate for the fuel parameters specified for Residual Marine Fuels in ISO 8217. Here, 12 out of 15 parameters can already be fulfilled through a simple distillation of the

TCR[®] oil. The water content, the flash point and Ignition Quality succeed the specified limits. A reduction of the water content and an increase in the flash point can be achieved as described before. An increase in the Ignition Quality is also likely to be reached by the application of a mild hydrotreatment of the distillate.

3.2 First results of the Synol process

Until now, one initial GTL trial was done with the described laboratory-plant at a temperature of 190°C and a pressure level of 25 bar. No reduction or activation of the produced iron catalyst was done prior to the experiment. The trial was run for 72 h. Figure 3 shows one analytical measurement at the start (blue bars) and one analytical measurement at the end of the trial (orange bars).

Figure 4: Measurement at the beginning and the end of the initial Synol trial at 190°C and 25 bar

It is worth mentioning that at the beginning of the initial conversion trial 2-hexanol (the main targeted product of the Synol process) can be detected by GC measurement. However, next to 2-hexanol a variety of other products (mainly other alcohols) are present. It is also important to note that carbon chains with less than seven carbon atoms (C1 – C7), have also been formed. However, they are not shown in Figure 3 as they were detected via the second FID. Comparing the GC-results with the measurement done at the end of the GTL trial, most of the initially detected products have significantly decreased in quantity. Only 2-hexanol and 2-heptanol show a strong increase in peak areas and thus in concentration within the sample.

The results from the initial trial show a promising tendency, that 2-hexanol can be produced via the Synol process even without a prior reduction or activation of the produced iron catalyst. The variety of products at the beginning of the trial can be attributed to potential contamination within the apparatus (leading to unintended reactions, resulting in the formation of alternative products) during the starting phase of the trial.

4 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The superior properties of the TCR[®] oil produced from biogenic feedstock “Herbaceous Mix” allow that a simple distillation already produces a fuel which is close to fulfill the specified parameters within the ISO 8217. Further refinement of the distillates can be reached via mild hydrotreatment, the addition of additives or the separation of the low-boiling distillation fraction. After receiving the results of the distillates produced from Jerusalem Artichoke and Sorghum, an analog comparison of the

properties and the requirements stated in ISO 8217 will be made.

In addition to that, the above-mentioned distillate upgrading methods will be individually evaluated and tested with the aim of developing an economic and sustainable way to produce standard Marine Fuels from biomass.

The Synol process is a promising method that, in contrast to comparable Gas to Liquid processes, can be operated under very mild conditions. The energetic advantage of this is evident. In this study, only the boundary conditions were explored in an initial conversion trial. It is essential to further investigate this process to determine optimal process parameters. Within this, the catalyst is a key component and optimization through activation and calcination might lead to a significant improvement of the process. Furthermore, it is planned to conduct experiments with modified process parameters, especially the process temperature and the process pressure to further increase in the 2-hexanol output. For this a parameter study will be conducted.

In general, it can be said that the developed innovative biorefinery enables the production of economic and sustainable biofuel precursors. Due to the superior quality of the intermediates produced through the thermo-catalytic reforming process, simple and economical upgrading processes can be used for a subsequent upgrade to standard biofuels.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] Kick, C., Kidikas, Ž., Kasiulienė, A., Maletić, S., Zeremski, T., Rubežius, M., ... & Ortner, M. (2024). Feasibility of using phytoremediation biomass for sustainable biofuel production via thermochemical conversion. *Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining*, 18(4), 1010-1026.
- [2] Rubežius, M., Kidikas, Ž., Kick, C., & Kasiulienė, A. (2025). Phytoremediation of Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons-Contaminated Soils: Case Study of Jerusalem Artichokes with Cost Analysis and Biomass Conversion. *Agronomy*, 15(3), 601.
- [3] Hornung, A., Jahangiri, H., Ouadi, M., Kick, C., Deinert, L., Meyer, B., ... & Eder, S. (2022). Thermo-Catalytic Reforming (TCR)–An important link between waste management and renewable fuels as part of the energy transition. *Applications in Energy and Combustion Science*, 12, 100088.
- [4] Kick, C., Uchaikina, A., Apfelbacher, A., Daschner, R., Helmreich, B., & Hornung, A. (2022). Aqueous phase of thermo-catalytic reforming of sewage sludge–quantity, quality, and its electrooxidative treatment by a boron-doped diamond electrode. *Separation and Purification Technology*, 286, 120392.
- [5] Wirz, C. F., Mundt, T., & Reders, K. (2021). Marine Fuels. *Handbook of Fuels: Energy Sources for Transportation*, 533-540.
- [6] Gollakota, A. R., Reddy, M., Subramanyam, M. D., & Kishore, N. (2016). A review on the upgradation techniques of pyrolysis oil. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 58, 1543-1568.
- [7] Prussi, M. (2024). Applying the International Maritime Organisation Life Cycle Assessment Guidelines to Pyrolysis Oil-Derived Blends: A Sustainable Option for Marine Fuels. *Energies*, 17(21), 5464.
- [8] Neumann, J., Binder, S., Apfelbacher, A., Gasson, J. R., García, P. R., & Hornung, A. (2015). Production and characterization of a new quality pyrolysis oil, char and syngas from digestate–Introducing the thermo-catalytic reforming process. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis*, 113, 137-142.
- [9] Borg, Ø., Hammer, N., Enger, B. C., Myrstad, R., Lindvåg, O. A., Eri, S., ... & Rytter, E. (2011). Effect of biomass-derived synthesis gas impurity elements on cobalt Fischer–Tropsch catalyst performance including in situ sulphur and nitrogen addition. *Journal of Catalysis*, 279(1), 163-173.
- [10] Dos Santos, R. G., & Alencar, A. C. (2020). Biomass-derived syngas production via gasification process and its catalytic conversion into fuels by Fischer Tropsch synthesis: A review. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 45(36), 18114-18132.
- [11] Kick, Christopher, et al. "Development and Commissioning of an Innovative Biorefinery for the Conversion of Contaminated Biomass into High-quality Energy Carriers." (2023).
- [12] Wenzel, Wilhelm: Das Synolverfahren. Eine neue Synthese aliphatischer Alkohole. In: *Angewandte Chemie*, 60. Year (1948), Nr. 9, P. 225-229
- [13] Freund, Hans-Joachim: Das SYNOL-Verfahren – vergessener Exot der Fischer-Tropsch-Chemie. In: *Nachrichten aus der Chemie*, 72. Year (2024), Paper 11, P. 28-31
- [14] I.G. Farbenindustrie A.G. (n.d). Report on Investigations by Fuels and Lubricants Teams at the I.G. Farbenindustrie A.G. Works at Leuna – Synol Process. In: *fischer-tropsch.org – Primary documents*. Retrieved June 13, 2025, from https://www.fischer-tropsch.org/primary_documents/gvt_reports/MofFP/ig_farb_at_leuna/ig_synol.htm

6 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101006912.

